

Asymmetric decay heat removal in MYRRHA: experiments in the E-SCAPE facility

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ABSTRACT

MYRRHA is an accelerator-driven system, coupling a proton accelerator to a subcritical reactor cooled by lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE), under development by SCK CEN in Belgium. The reactor design is based on a pool configuration, all components of the primary system housed within the main vessel. In this context, the thermal-hydraulic experimental program considers separately the performance of individual reactor components, and the integral pool dynamics in steady-state and in anticipated transients.

The E-SCAPE (European SCAled Pool Experiment) facility is a thermal hydraulic 1/6-scale model of the primary system of the MYRRHA reactor. Replicas of the main components are placed in the main vessel, while pumps and heat exchangers are located in two external circuits. Operating conditions in LBE are representative of (scaled) decay heat removal in terms of mass flow rate (up to 120 kg/s), core power (up to 100 kW) and temperature (200 – 340 °C). This arrangement allows the study of different scenarios, including forced circulation, natural circulation, flow transitions and asymmetric operation.

Two specific asymmetric scenarios, corresponding to possible initiating events for design-basis accidents, are studied in the present experimental campaign, framed within the European collaborative project PASCAL (2020-2024). First, a single pump failure is investigated. Second, partial loss of heat sink is simulated by stopping the flow of secondary coolant in only one circuit. These scenarios are compared to a reference symmetric case. Their evolution depends on the fluid mixing in the cold and hot plena.

KEYWORDS

MYRRHA, LBE, experiment, pool, asymmetric

1. INTRODUCTION

The Belgian Nuclear Research Center (SCK CEN) is developing MYRRHA, a subcritical fast reactor cooled by lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE) coupled to a proton accelerator, in an accelerator-driven system (ADS) setup [1]. Relevant for the thermal-hydraulic analysis, the primary coolant system is arranged in a pool configuration, with all components housed within the main vessel and inserted from the top, penetrating through the reactor cover. Supporting the reactor design and safety assessment, thermal-hydraulic experiments and simulations at different scales are necessary [2]. Fundamental and separate-effect tests allow the investigation of basic phenomena like turbulent heat transfer in liquid metals. Prototypical component tests focus on the behavior of a given component. Integral tests represent the dynamic evolution of the system accounting for the interaction between components.

This article deals with asymmetric flow scenarios that might occur in anticipated design-basis accidents, such as the failure of one single pump in the primary circuit, or partial loss of heat sink if one secondary cooling circuit is inactive. For this study it is important to study the pool as an integral system, because the interaction of individual components and overall geometry determine the thermal-hydraulic evolution of the transient, particularly in conditions of natural circulation.

An experimental campaign focused on asymmetric heat removal was completed in the E-SCAPE test facility [3]. This experimental setup, described in §2, is a 1/6 scaled mockup of MYRRHA. The boundary conditions and experimental procedure for selected cases are given in §3. The results for individual cases are presented in §4 to §7 and compared in §8. Concluding remarks are summarized in §9.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP: THE E-SCAPE FACILITY

A geometry scaling ratio of 1:6 was selected based on a non-dimensional similarity analysis, maintaining the pressure loss characteristics (Euler number) and the ratio of buoyant to inertial forces (i.e. Richardson number) in natural circulation as in MYRRHA [4]. The main vessel with an outer diameter of 1400mm and a height of 2100mm is coupled to external circuits, as sketched in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic layout of the E-SCAPE facility. The main vessel is a 1/6 mockup of MYRRHA and the external circuits provide relevant boundary conditions

In contrast to MYRRHA, LBE pumps and heat exchangers in E-SCAPE are placed in external circuits connecting to the primary vessel through dummy channels. This configuration is imposed by the limited space inside the main vessel and it is exploited to increase the height difference between the heat source (core simulator) and heat sink (heat exchangers), improving the similarity of buoyancy forces. These circuits provide relevant boundary conditions of LBE flow rate (up to 60 kg/s each) and inlet temperature to the lower plenum of the main vessel. Moreover, these have been design to maintain similarity with respect to the Richardson number, representing the ratio of buoyant to inertial forces. Return lines into the vessel are thermally insulated from the upper plenum in order to avoid disruption of the natural circulation. In transient conditions, the transit time through the circuits must be taken into account in the analysis. In order to obtain an accurate estimation of this flow-through times, a hot-plug can be suddenly released via a three-way valve in loop A (left in Figure 1). Although loops A and B are not identical, throttle valves are adjusted in order to obtain equal pressure loss characteristics.

The secondary coolant in E-SCAPE is a high-flash point thermal oil, in contrast to the water/steam mixture at 16 bar and 200°C used in MYRRHA. A single-phase oil circuit allows for a simpler operation, but it cannot reproduce the condition of constant saturation temperature characteristic of steam generators. Given the large heat capacity of the oil (DURATHERM HF, physical properties available in [5]) and high oil flow rates in the circuit, its temperature increase across the heat exchangers (2x30 kW in each loop) is nominally less than 3.0 K, thus reproducing the boundary conditions in the reactor reasonably well. One air cooler with a capacity of 60 kW is directly upstream of each oil pump. The oil circuits can be operated independently, or they can be arranged in a configuration where only one oil pump feeds two heat exchangers and both air coolers. This setup allows studying asymmetric scenarios like a heat exchanger failure (see §3), while keeping the maximum cooling capacity of both air coolers.

An electric core simulator with a maximum capacity of 100 kW is installed in the main vessel. The core geometry is simplified, with heating wires mounted on concentric cylindrical structures and an inlet grid designed for maintaining similar pressure losses as in the reactor. This available heating power in the core simulator corresponds to the scaled decay power immediately after scram (ca. 7% of nominal power) in MYRRHA. Thus, the conditions that can be established in E-SCAPE are representative of protected accidental scenarios for the study of natural circulation, preserving buoyancy effects.

An overview of the installed instrumentation is shown in Figure 2. A major focus is placed on temperature measurements, with 350 type K thermo-couples (TCs), in addition to those needed for heat tracing. These are distributed along the inner wall of the main vessel (46), the diaphragm and baffle (67), in the silicon doping mockup (SD, 84), the core simulator and above core structure (17), the inlet and outlet channels (56), the fuel handling machines mockups (FHM, 25), instrumentation rods mounted from the top cover and reaching the upper plenum (30), the LBE circuits (10 for loop A and 7 for loop B) and oil circuits (8, 4 each). The standard accuracy for type K TCs is ± 1.5 K, although this can be improved by a calibration procedure. For all TCs in contact with LBE, a *relative in-situ* calibration is performed by imposing a large flow rate that guarantees good thermal mixing in isothermal conditions. One single TC is selected as a reference (vessel inlet temperature loop A) and the temperature differences are recorded as offsets. This procedure allows reducing the *relative uncertainty* to less than ± 0.2 K. The TCs in the oil circuit are calibrated in an oven, to an *absolute uncertainty* of ± 0.2 K.

Moreover, two radar level sensors (with an accuracy of ± 3.0 mm each) are mounted on the top cover to monitor the free surface in the upper and lower (actually measured in a FHM mockup) plena. An absolute pressure sensor measures the pressure in the cover gas (nitrogen), nominally at 4.5 bar(g) as needed to maintain the external circuit filled with LBE. Differential pressure sensors are installed at several positions in the vessel and in the circuits, for example across the core. The LBE flow rate in each loop is measured by a Coriolis sensor ($\pm 0.1\%$), and Vortex flow meters ($\pm 0.65\%$) are installed in the oil circuits.

Furthermore, 45 positions for local velocity measurements with UDV sensors are available in the lower plenum. However, these UDV sensors have not yet been successfully qualified and commissioned.

Figure 2. Overview of instrumentation in the main vessel. Left: vertical planes. Right: top view of the cover. Flanges A to F correspond to thermo-couples in the upper plenum and cover gas. Other flanges are used for level (L), oxygen (O) and pressure (P) sensors.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE: SELECTED CASES

The test matrix for the E-SCAPE facility covers several types of transient and steady-state cases [6], including calibration and hot-plug tests for further verification of flow-through times. The present work focuses on three scenarios, each connecting two steady-states via a transient, as summarized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Summary of selected cases describing 3 scenarios (case numbers for traceability only). All relevant steady-state boundary conditions are listed in Table I.

For all three scenarios, the initial conditions are the same, a symmetric forced circulation steady-state, described in detail in §4. From hot stand-by conditions, the speed of both LBE and both oil pumps is controlled to maintain constant flow rates. The core heater is maintained at a constant power, and the speed of air coolers is controlled to maintain constant LBE inlet temperatures (in each loop) into the main vessel. This process requires up to 4 hours for all signals to stabilize, then the stable steady-state is recorded during 5 to 10 minutes. A practical consequence of this long waiting period is that these three scenarios are studied in different days. This means that environmental conditions (e.g. room temperature) might be different and potentially influence the results (e.g. via the thermal losses). Post-processing of the data confirms that the conditions are identical (within the experimental uncertainty) for all three cases. Therefore, only one of these cases is analyzed.

Prior to starting the transient, the control system of the air coolers is changed from monitoring the LBE temperature to maintaining a constant oil inlet temperature to the heat exchangers (in each loop). This scheme is representative of the transient evolution in MYRRHA, because the two-phase secondary circuit maintains a constant saturation temperature and the primary circuit evolves toward new stable conditions. Between 5 and 10 minutes after starting to record data, one of the three actions is performed in order to trigger a transient scenario. In the first test, both LBE pumps are stopped, leading to a **symmetric loss of flow (LOF)** scenario. This is an important reference case in order to better understand the behavior of the asymmetric cases. In a second test, a **single pump failure (SPF)** is triggered by stopping the LBE pump in loop B. The third test simulates a **heat exchanger failure (HXF)** by stopping the oil circuit in loop B and closing the associated flow control valve, so that the oil flow rate is effectively zero.

The transient evolution is recorded during 2 to 3 hours, while the most relevant phenomena are observed in the initial 20 minutes. These transients converge towards a new steady state, which is also recorded during 10 minutes. The only exception is the heat exchanger failure test, as the oil in loop B continuously cools down with zero flow. For that reason, the stable steady-state condition associated to the HXF is studied separately, with an asymmetric configuration of the oil circuits, as described in §2. The boundary conditions and selected results for the steady states are listed in Table I.

Table I. Selected boundary conditions and results for the four steady states, corresponding to the initial and final conditions of the three transient scenarios shown in Figure 3.

Parameter	Forced Circulation	Natural Circulation	Single Pump Failure (SPF)	Heat Exchanger Failure (HXF)
Case number	41	43	50	36
Core thermal power (kW)	73.0 ± 0.7	73.0 ± 0.7	73.0 ± 0.7	73.0 ± 0.7
LBE flow rate loop A (kg/s)	46.61 ± 0.05	4.097 ± 0.009	46.60 ± 0.05	46.60 ± 0.05
LBE flow rate loop B (kg/s)	46.60 ± 0.05	4.103 ± 0.009	-0.712 ± 0.008	46.60 ± 0.05
Oil flow rate loop A (kg/s)	6.00 ± 0.04	6.00 ± 0.04	6.00 ± 0.04	6.00 ± 0.04
Oil flow rate loop B (kg/s)	6.00 ± 0.04	6.00 ± 0.04	6.00 ± 0.04	0.003 ± 0.001
LBE inlet temperature A (°C)	200.01 ± 0.06	182.82 ± 0.06	211.17 ± 0.06	200.01 ± 0.06
LBE inlet temperature B (°C)	199.9 ± 0.1	183.9 ± 0.1	209.1 ± 0.1	208.7 ± 0.1
LBE outlet temperature A (°C)	206 ± 3	241 ± 3	219 ± 3	210 ± 3
LBE outlet temperature B (°C)	205 ± 3	238 ± 3	212 ± 3	209 ± 3
Oil inlet temperature A (°C)	168.7 ± 0.2	168.7 ± 0.2	169.1 ± 0.2	131.5 ± 0.2
Oil inlet temperature B (°C)	171.7 ± 0.1	171.3 ± 0.1	172.5 ± 0.1	129.9 ± 0.1
Oil outlet temperature A (°C)	167.8 ± 0.2	167.5 ± 0.2	168.8 ± 0.2	134.3 ± 0.2
Oil outlet temperature B (°C)	174.5 ± 0.3	174.1 ± 0.3	173.9 ± 0.3	107.6 ± 0.3
LBE level difference (mm)	138 ± 7	0 ± 7	28 ± 7	136 ± 7

In all cases, the acquisition rate is every 0.3 seconds. The reported experimental uncertainty combines a contribution from the sensor itself (after calibration) and a minor one related to the resolution of the analog-to-digital signal converter, which only plays a relevant role for few individual TCs. Moreover, the statistical component (noise) is taken into account for the uncertainty of the average in a steady state.

4. REFERENCE STEADY-STATE SYMMETRIC FORCED CIRCULATION

The reference symmetric forced circulation case is the initial condition for all transients scenarios. A temperature map for all 320 TCs in the LBE in the main vessel is shown in Figure 4. For reference and for a better understanding of the vertical planes, a larger number of TCs are placed near the flow discharge of loop A into the lower plenum, as these signals are relevant for the analysis of the hot-plug tests. Moreover, the coordinate system for the horizontal planes (top views) is indicated.

Figure 4. Temperature map in the main vessel for the forced circulation symmetric steady state

In this scenario, the LBE flow is rather large (2×46.6 kg/s, corresponding to 80% of the nominal flow) and therefore the temperature difference between the hot leg (upper plenum) and cold leg (lower plenum) in the LBE is only ~ 5.0 K, see Table I. Higher temperatures are only observed locally in the core region and above core structure. The maximum core wall temperature is 233.7 °C. Although the core geometry and power density is not identical as in MYRRHA, the wall-to-fluid temperature difference is similar.

At these large flow rates, buoyancy forces are negligible with respect to inertial forces; temperature is transported by the flow like a scalar. Because the flow scenario is symmetric, the temperature in the lower plenum is homogeneous. The upper plenum is also well mixed, as there is no clear stratification visible.

The level difference in this reference case is 138.0 mm, with the level in the lower plenum (annulus) higher than in the upper plenum. This level difference corresponds to the pressure drop across the core.

5. LOSS OF FLOW TRANSIENT AND NATURAL CIRCULATION STEADY-STATE

From an initial condition of symmetric forced circulation, a **LOF** scenario is triggered by suddenly stopping both LBE pumps (shutting off electrical power supply). It should be noted that in a previous campaign [6], a throttle valve was also closed and a bypass valve was opened (see Figure 1) in order to avoid the pressure losses across the pump itself in each LBE loop. However, the duration of this manual operation (up to 60 seconds) is considered too long, as during this period the pressure loss characteristics are unknown. Thus, these new experiments are performed without using the bypass valves.

Figure 5 shows the evolution in time of the most relevant variables for the analysis of the LOF transient during 1 hour. The first 10 minutes correspond to the initial steady state (forced circulation). Both LBE pumps are switched off at time $t_0=605$ s, their speed is recorded to reach zero at $t=t_0+7$ s.

Figure 5. Evolution of selected variables for the Loss Of Flow transient scenario

The immediate consequence of the LBE pumps slowing down is that the pressure head is reduced. As a consequence, the level difference cannot be maintained and liquid inventory is transferred from the lower plenum (annulus) to the upper plenum through the core. A complete equalization of the levels is observed at $t=t_0+22$ s, and the difference remains zero throughout the rest of the scenario.

Since the level difference is the main driving force for the flow across the core in forced circulation, the LBE flow rate in both circuits is also reduced in the same time scale, but it never reaches zero. The minimum LBE flow rate measured in loop A is 1.3 kg/s at $t=t_0+35$ s, and at loop B is 1.5 kg/s at $t=t_0+44$ s. These minimum values of the flow rate are driven by the buoyancy forces between the hot and cold legs present in the initial forced circulation steady-state, where the temperature difference was only 5.0 K, as discussed in §4. As this is a symmetric case, the LBE flow rate is similar in loops A and B throughout the complete scenario.

During the initial 2 to 4 minutes, the LBE temperatures measured in the circuits at the inlet and outlet of the main vessel are not affected by the change in flow rate. This delay is related to the transit time for the LBE from the heat source (core simulator) and sink (heat exchangers) to the individual TC positions.

Indeed loop B (dashed lines in Figure 5) reacts faster than loop A (solid lines). Initially the LBE inlet temperature to the main vessel decreases due to the behavior of the LBE-to-oil heat exchangers after a sudden reduction in the LBE flow rate: the LBE outlet temperature (inlet to the vessel) is also reduced and the total power transported across the heat exchanger is lower. Maintaining the oil flow rate constant, also the oil outlet temperature is reduced. The controllers of the air coolers aim to maintain the oil inlet temperature to the heat exchanger constant, yet an initial drop up to 5.0 K is observed.

The LBE inlet temperature to the vessel is reduced and the outlet temperature is increased in both loops. As this temperature difference increases, larger buoyancy forces drive a higher mass flow rates. In both loops, the LBE flow rate stabilizes at 4.1 kg/s at $t=t_0+806$ s. Both inlet and outlet temperatures continue evolving with minor changes after $t=2500$ s, but their difference remains constant, and therefore also the flow rate.

A maximum core temperature of 342 °C is reached at $t=t_0+78$ s, that is only 53 s after the minimum flow rates are measured. As the flow rates increase, the maximum core temperature decreases towards a new stable value. Recording of this transient lasts for two hours, then stable conditions are observed and the natural circulation steady state is recorded as a separate case during 10 minutes. The resulting temperature map for the natural circulation case is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Temperature map in the main vessel for the loss of flow steady-state (natural circulation).

A homogeneous temperature in the lower plenum is observed in Figure 6, because this natural circulation scenario is symmetric. Compared to the reference forced-circulation case, the total flow rate is reduced to only 8.8% (4.1 kg/s in each loop) and consequently, at a constant power, the temperature difference between cold and hot legs increases by almost a factor 12 (~60 K vs. ~5 K). Indeed, the cold leg temperature is ~20 K lower and the hot leg temperature 35 K higher than in the forced-circulation scenario (see Table I). This change in both cold and hot leg temperatures is explained by the boundary condition of constant oil temperature at the heat exchangers.

All horizontal planes in Figure 6 show homogeneous temperature outside of the core region. Moreover, thermal stratification is observed in the upper plenum, as later described in detail in §8.

6. SINGLE PUMP FAILURE TRANSIENT AND STEADY-STATE

Figure 6 shows the evolution in time of the most relevant variables for the analysis of the **SPF** transient during 1 hour. The first 7 minutes correspond to the initial steady state (forced circulation). The LBE pump in loop B is stopped at time $t_0=452$ s, and its speed is recorded to reach zero at $t=t_0+7$ s.

Figure 7. Evolution of selected variables for the Single Pump Failure transient scenario

The LBE flow rate in loop B decreases rapidly and reaches zero and even negative values (-0.71 kg/s) at $t=t_0+13$ s. Even larger reversed flow rates might be possible, but this cannot be confirmed experimentally because the sensor signal is saturated at its lowest value. A further indication of reversed flow in loop B is that the temperature of the hot leg (vessel outlet) becomes lower than that of the cold leg (vessel inlet) at $t=t_0+89$ s. The order is again reversed at $t=t_0+281$ s, yet the flow meter remains at its lowest limit in all the transient.

In loop A, the flow rate increases slightly initially arguably influenced by the reversed flow in loop B, since buoyancy effects are not yet relevant in such a short time scale. The rotational speed of the pump is controlled to maintain a constant flow rate (46.6 kg/s) and it is observed to be reduced by 2.1%. The level difference decreases from 138 mm to 28 mm. It is noted that while the total flow rate is a factor 0.5 of the original value, the level difference stabilizes at a factor 0.2. Although this one single experiment is not statistically significant, the scaling of level difference with flow rate seems to have an exponent higher than 2.0, which indicates the influence of buoyancy forces.

After $t=t_0+281$ s, the transient temperatures evolve slowly following the dynamics of the controller for the air cooler aiming to maintain the oil temperature constant. Recording continues for 165 minutes until stable conditions are observed, with a maximum core temperature of 276 °C.

Figure 8 shows the temperature map for the SPF steady state. Since this is an asymmetric scenario, the LBE flow rate in loop A is much larger than in loop B. Thus, the temperature in the lower plenum is eventually homogenized to the value of the inlet vessel temperature from loop A. Compared to the forced circulation case, higher temperatures are observed in the upper plenum following the heat balance.

Figure 8. Temperature map in the main vessel for the single pump failure steady-state

7. HEAT EXCHANGER FAILURE TRANSIENT AND STEADY-STATE

Figure 9 shows the evolution in time of the most relevant variables for the analysis of the **HXF** transient during 1 hour. The first 7 minutes correspond to the initial steady state (forced circulation). The oil pump in loop B is stopped at time $t_0=399$ s. The associated flow-control valve is also closed, and the oil flow rate reaches zero at $t=t_0+61$ s. The LBE pumps continue operating in the same regime, and the LBE flow rates and level difference remain constant for the complete duration of the transient.

At $t=t_0+17$ s, the vessel inlet temperature in loop B starts increasing, as a consequence of reducing the cooling power of the heat exchangers. The oil in these heat exchangers acts as a finite heat sink, heating up until reaching equilibrium with the LBE. When this occurs, the LBE in loop B re-enter the vessel nearly at the same temperature as it exits it (with a minor difference due to heat losses), effectively stopping cooling from loop B.

At a constant heating power, and with all the cooling load imposed on loop A, the temperature difference between its hot and cold legs increases. Moreover, the average LBE temperature in loop A must also increase in order to achieve an adequate difference with the oil temperature, which allows exchange the nominal thermal power through a smaller heat exchanging area. This transient was recorded during 200 minutes and stable conditions were not obtained, yet temperatures were observed to approach an asymptotic value. At this stage it is important to recall that the stagnant oil in loop B is in thermal equilibrium with the LBE hot leg. In order not to exceed safety limits with respect to the oil temperature, the transient was stopped.

Figure 9. Evolution of selected variables for the Heat Exchanger Failure transient scenario

A stable steady-state was recorded on a different day, setting the controller of the air cooler to maintain a constant value of 200°C for the LBE inlet temperature in loop A. This effectively leads to a colder oil temperature than targeted for the transient scenario. Thus, this steady-state case is analogous to the asymptotic result of the previous transient, although with an offset towards lower temperatures overall. A temperature map for this steady-state HXF scenario is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Temperature map in the main vessel for the single pump failure steady state

For this scenario, thermal mixing is observed in the lower plenum. From loop A, LBE enters at the cold leg temperature (200.0 °C) and from loop B, at the hot leg temperature (208.8°C, see Table I). The mixed inlet temperature to the core is 204.4 °C, and since the total LBE flow rate is the same (2×46.6 kg/s), all temperatures in the upper plenum are 4 to 5 K higher than in the reference forced circulation case. The maximum core temperature is 274°C. Thermal stratification is not observed in the upper plenum.

8. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS: SELECTED FEATURES OF STEADY STATE SCENARIOS

The temperature maps shown in §4 to §7 display many TCs and only allow a general overview of the temperature distribution in the main vessel. In the present §8, two specific temperature profiles are analyzed in further detail, comparing the four steady-state cases described in the previous sections. Figure 11 shows temperature profiles in the vertical direction along the upper plenum and the cover gas, measured with sensors mounted on TC rods E and F from the top, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 11. Temperature profile in the vertical direction along the upper plenum and cover gas

In both forced circulation and HXF scenarios, the LBE temperature in the upper plenum is homogeneous, because the high flow rate (2×46.6 kg/s) promotes thermal mixing. It is recalled here that the difference between both temperature levels is *only* ~5 K because the oil temperature was purposely reduced in order to avoid reaching excessively high temperature in the loop with zero oil flow, as described in §7. In the natural circulation case, the upper plenum is stratified, with the hotter liquid collecting at the top near the free surface. In a pool-type reactor, this result is undesired because potentially the hotter stagnant liquid might not participate in the heat exchanger to the secondary coolant, and large temperature gradients can affect the mechanical integrity of some structures. Nevertheless, the highest temperature in the upper plenum in this case is only slight higher (~5 K) than the vessel outlet temperature. Understandably, the results for the SPF scenario show an intermediate degree of thermal stratification in the upper plenum.

The cover gas is *inversely* stratified, with the highest gas temperatures at the bottom and coldest at the top. This arrangement is not stable, as buoyancy flow patterns triggered by instabilities would lead to thermal mixing. However, it is maintained because of the heat losses at the top cover.

Figure 12 shows the temperature profiles at the outlet of the core ($y=330$ mm), which consists of heating wires mounted on concentric cylindrical structures. Like in the upper plenum (Figure 11), the temperature profiles for the forced circulation and HXF cases are nearly identical, with a constant offset of ~ 5 K. This is an indication of perfect thermal mixing in the upper plenum for the cases with high LBE flow rate.

Figure 12. Temperature profile in the radial profile at the outlet of the core simulator

The shape of the temperature profile represents the balance between the flow distribution among the ring channels and the distribution of power among the individual heaters, which remains constant for all cases. Only for the natural circulation case, where buoyancy effects are dominant the trend is clearly descending from hottest in the center to coldest in the edge. Although this results cannot be directly extrapolated to MYRRHA (due to the different core geometry), it is relevant for the validation of numerical simulations.

9. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental campaign was recently completed at the E-SCAPE facility focusing on asymmetric flow scenarios representative of postulated design-basis accidents for the MYRRHA reactor. A single pump failure (SPF) and heat exchanger failure (HXF) are studied and compared to a symmetric loss of flow (LOF). All cases share the same initial conditions of symmetric forced circulation.

The operating conditions in the E-SCAPE facility (LBE inlet temperature, flow rate, buoyancy effects) are representative of decay heat removal in MYRRHA. In all studied cases, decay heat can be safely removed from the core, as the maximum core temperature measured in the LBE transient is only 342 °C. The current analysis is focused on the evolution of the most relevant variables, such as LBE inlet and outlet temperature to the vessel and mass flow rates. In the case of SPF, reversed flow is observed in the side where the LBE pump is stopped. Although the signal of the flow meter is saturated at its lowest limit, a hotter temperature is observed in the cold leg then in the hot leg and later the situation is reversed. In the case of HXF, all thermal power generated in the core can be cooled by means of only one LBE circuit, with a corresponding increase in LBE temperature.

Due to the extensive amount of instrumentation, with 320 TCs installed in the main vessel, these experiments are designed for direct comparison with numerical simulations. Particularly considering that the reactor design has evolved slightly since the E-SCAPE facility was first commissioned, validation of simulation tools in representative conditions is essential for the safety assessment and licensing process.

NOMENCLATURE

ADS	Accelerator Driven System	LP	Lower Plenum
FC	Forced Circulation	NC	Natural Circulation
FHM	Fuel Handling Machine	SD	Silicon Doping
HXF	Heat Exchanger Failure	SPF	Single Pump Failure
IP	Intermediate Plenum	t	Time [s]
LBE	Lead Bismuth Eutectic	UDV	Ultrasonic Doppler Velocimetry
LOF	Loss Of Flow	UP	Upper Plenum

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REFERENCES

1. D. De Bruyn, H.A. Abderrahim, M. Schyns, "Recent progress and perspectives in the Belgian MYRRHA ADS programme", Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Advances in Nuclear Power Plants (ICAPP2019), Juan-les-pin, France, May 12-15, 2019 (2019)
2. J. Pacio, K. Van Tichelen, G. Kennedy, M. Iarmonov, D. Rozzia, P. Schuurmans, R. Fernandez, "Experimental thermal-hydraulic R&D achievements and needs for MYRRHA"
3. K. Van Tichelen, F. Mirelli, M. Greco, G. Viviani, "E-SCAPE: A scale facility for liquid-metal, pool-type reactor thermal hydraulic investigations". *Nucl. Eng. and Design* **290**, pp. 65-77 (2015)
4. K. Van Tichelen, M. Vanderhaegen, S. Jajarayu, S. Keijers, F. Roelofs, "Scaling analysis for the European heavy liquid metal scaled pool facility E-SCAPE". 14th International Topical Meeting on Nuclear Reactor Thermal-Hydraulics (NURETH-14), Toronto, September 25-30, 2011
5. Duratherm High Flash Thermal Oil: www.durathermfluids.com/products/duratherm-hf/
6. K. Van Tichelen, F. Mirelli, "Results on thermal hydraulic experiments in the LBE-cooled scaled pool facility E-SCAPE in support of the MYRRHA design and licensing". 18th International Topical Meeting on Nuclear Reactor Thermal Hydraulics, Portland, OR, United States, August 18-23, 2019.